

SSHOC-NL T4.2 deliverable 2024-D02:

Getty AAT Concepts in DANS Data Station

Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH)

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Links

- AATC in DANS SKOMOS browser: <https://vocabs.datastations.nl/AATC/en/>
- Development git repository: <https://github.com/DANS-KNAW/Getty-AAT-Concepts>

The Getty Arts & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT)

What is the AAT?

The [Getty Arts & Architecture Thesaurus](#) is a multilingual, semantically structured **controlled vocabulary**. It encompasses terms, descriptions, and other information for generic concepts related to visual art, architecture, archaeology, and other cultural heritage. Importantly, the AAT contains generic terms, not iconographic subjects or proper names. In other words: [“each concept is a case of many \(a generic thing\), not a case of one \(a specific thing\)”](#). The full AAT database contains around 74,460 concept records (subject_id) and 503,230 terms (term_id). Each concept record contains one or more terms (e.g., singular/plural forms, spelling variations, translations). A record minimally contains a unique numeric id, a term, and an indication for the position in the structured hierarchy. Often it also contains a description of the term, a list of associated or equivalent terms and temporal information. The AAT is translated to Dutch by the Netherlands Institute for Art History. Note that the AAT is a compiled resource, so it's not a complete, definitive collection of concepts. It expands through community [contributions](#) by domain experts.

Terminology

Here you find a list of the most important entity types (classes) of the AAT. The terms relate to the different layers of information in the thesaurus.

- **Facet:** The major subdivision or upper layer of AAT's hierarchical structure, each containing classes of concepts. In total, there are 8 facets.
- **Hierarchy:** Groupings of terminology that are arranged within the facets.
- **Guide Term:** A placeholder for categories within the hierarchies. They serve to organize the hierarchies into logical segments.
- **Record:** A single entry that contains information about a specific concept.
- **Term:** A word or phrase that represents the concept in the record. Includes singular/plural forms, spelling variations, and translations. A record can contain multiple terms.

This example illustrates how the different levels work: - Facet: [Agents](#) - Hierarchy: [People \(hierarchy name\)](#) - Guide Term: [< people by occupation >](#) - Record: [taxonomists](#) - Term: [taxonoom \(Dutch\)](#)

Take a look at this example record as seen from an end-user's perspective, exhibiting some of the entity types (classes) instances.

Sample AAT "Record" Display for the End-User

Record ID: 198841

Descriptor: rhyta

Note: Refers to vessels from Ancient Greece, eastern Europe, or the Middle East that typically have a closed form with two openings, one at the top for filling and one at the base so that liquid could stream out. They are often in the shape of a horn or an animal's head, and were typically used as a drinking cup or for pouring wine into another vessel.

Hierarchy:

Containers [TQ]

...<containers by function or context>

.....<culinary containers>

.....<containers for serving and consuming food>

Terms:

rhyta (preferred)

rhyton (alternate, singular)

protomai

protome

rhea

rheon

rheons

Related concepts:

stirrup cups

sturzbechers

drinking vessels

ceremonial vessels

[Image source](#), p32.

What does the AAT contain?

The AAT is structured as a hierarchical database of concepts, containing seven **facets** that each host a number of **hierarchies**. Below you can see an outline of the facets and hierarchies, including example terms. See [here](#) for a collapsible hierarchy display on the Getty website. It allows you to browse through the structure and inspect the leaf nodes. You may see that each facet has its own internal logic to order the nodes (e.g. on function, geographical, temporal or cultural information).

The root of the structure is called *Top of the AAT hierarchies*. Each facet in the table below contains a clickable link to their hierarchy on the Getty website.

Most facets are relatively straightforward in their meaning. The final facet, *Brand Names*, allows for necessary additions by the conservation community, particularly where a material, process, or object does not have a generic name and the names are under trademark protection. The largest facet is the *Objects* facet.

- [Root](#): **Top of the AAT hierarchies**
 - [ASSOCIATED CONCEPT](#) FACET
(e.g. *beauty, socialism, cultural pluralism*)
 - Associated Concepts
 - [PHYSICAL ATTRIBUTES](#) FACET
(e.g. *borders, round, waterlogged*)
 - Attributes and Properties
 - Conditions and Effects
 - Design Elements
 - Color
 - [STYLES AND PERIODS](#) FACET
(e.g. *Abstract Expressionist, Yoruba*)
 - Styles and Periods
 - [AGENTS](#) FACET
(e.g. *printmakers, landscape architects*)
 - People
 - Organizations
 - Living Organisms
 - [ACTIVITIES](#) FACET
(e.g. *archaeology, engineering, analyzing*)
 - Disciplines
 - Functions
 - Events
 - Physical and Mental Activities
 - Processes and Techniques
 - [MATERIALS](#) FACET
(e.g. *iron, clay, artificial ivory*)
 - Materials

- [OBJECTS](#) FACET
(e.g. *paintings, facades, cathedrals, chairs*)
 - Object Groupings and Systems
 - Object Genres
 - Components
 - Built Environment
 - Settlements and Landscapes
 - Built Complexes and Districts
 - Single Built Works
 - Open Spaces and Site Elements
 - Furnishings and Equipment
 - Furnishings
 - Costume
 - Tools and Equipment
 - Weapons and Ammunition
 - Measuring Devices
 - Containers
 - Sound Decides
 - Recreational Artifacts
 - Transportation Vehicles
 - Visual and Verbal Communication
 - Visual Works
 - Exchange Media
 - Information Forms
- [BRAND NAMES](#) FACET
(e.g. *Agfacolor, Arches paper*)
 - Brand Names

Taking a look under the hood: a Turtle file

The AAT was originally released in XML and Relational Table formats. More recently, it has been made available as [Linked Open Data \(LOD\)](#) in JSON, RDF, N3/Turtle, and N-Triples formats. It's recommended to not work with the XML or Relational Table formats because they may become obsolete in the future. The LOD options are the more robust choice.

Let's take a look at what a single record can look like in [Turtle](#) (Terse RDF Triple Language, or .ttl) format. Turtle is a syntax for expressing data in the Resource Description Framework (RDF), which is used to represent information about resources in the web and data interchange. Turtle is designed to be more human-readable compared to other RDF syntaxes, like XML. Turtle supports the use of URIs to uniquely identify concepts, improving data retrieval and linking related information.

Open the [aat_300123559.ttl](#) file in a new window and try to identify the following information:

- The record identifier
- The label name
- The date of the most recent modification
- The parent label
- The Dutch translations

You may have found that the record identifier is *300123559*, the label name *Attributes and Properties (hierarchy name)*, the date of the most recent modification *2015-07-03*, and the parent label *Physical Attributes Facet*. The Dutch translations of the terms and the descriptions are accessible through the @nl tags.

How can the AAT be used?

The AAT can be downloaded in various formats for local use, but more integrated options are available, such as the SPARQL Endpoint and the API. See the sections below with information on how to use them.

SPARQL Endpoint

With the SPARQL Endpoint you can take advantage of the linked data principles that are integrated in the AAT, and it allows you to perform complex queries.

- SPARQL UI: <https://vocab.getty.edu/sparql>
- SPARQL endpoint: <http://vocab.getty.edu/sparql>

API

API Documentation: <http://vocabsservices.getty.edu/AATService.asmx>

The AAT also offers an API (Application Programming Interface), a tool that allows developers to access and manipulate data programmatically. This makes it easier to integrate into applications and websites.

The API provides a straightforward way to retrieve specific information, such as related terms or hierarchical structures. It supports various operations, including **GetChildren** and **GetParents**, which allow you to explore the relationships between concepts. The API supports different protocols like **SOAP** and **HTTP**.

To get started with the API, you can try out the [GetChildren](#) operation on their website. You can enter any subject ID, for example 300015646.

Negative aspects of Getty API?

- responses are in XML (a bit antiquated and a pain to parse)
- limited number of API methods
- soon obsolete: in a [Getty LOD pages](#) it is stated (Dec.2024) that they will be updating Getty Vocabularies tech infrastructure, and retiring the XML (aka this API) at the end of 2025
- information present in the API response, is rather poor, when compared to what the SPARQL-endpoint RDF files/dump return
- no Dutch(NL) label is returned
- no (immediately visible) information on the class of the term - is it a skos:Concept or is it a skos:Collection?

AAT License: ODC-By

All Getty Vocabulary data found on this site are made available openly and free from fees under the [Open Data Commons Attribution License \(ODC-By\) 1.0](#).

Source: https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/obtain/index.html#citing_vocab

According to the [ODC-By license summary](#):

You are free:

- To share: To copy, distribute and use the database.
- To create: To produce works from the database.
- To adapt: To modify, transform and build upon the database.

As long as you:

- **Attribute:** You must attribute any public use of the database, or works produced from the database, in the manner specified in the license. For any use or redistribution of the database, or works produced from it, you must make clear to others the license of the database and keep intact any notices on the original database.

How to cite AAT

To attribute the Getty AAT under the Open Data Commons Attribution License (ODC-By) 1.0, please use the following statement: *Contains information from the J. Paul Getty Trust, Getty Research Institute, the Art & Architecture Thesaurus, which is made available under the [ODC Attribution License](#).*

The AAT in other projects

- [Termennetwerk](#): This project presents a Dutch search engine for terms and links them to their URIs in various thesauri, including the AAT.
- [Europeana](#): An online information portal that provides access to millions of cultural heritage resources by aggregating metadata from museums, libraries, and archives across Europe. A part of their records are encoded with AAT URIs, which they use to retrieve translations of the records ([source](#)).
- [A Methodology for Semantic Enrichment of Cultural Heritage Images Using Artificial Intelligence Technologies](#): This paper proposes a methodology for analyzing and enriching a collection of cultural images, specifically focusing on food in a cultural context. It combines the use of ontologies, including the AAT, to consistently represent concepts alongside Computer Vision tools to enhance image descriptions.
- [“Linking HBIM Graphical and Semantic Information Through the Getty AAT”](#): This study explores the integration of graphical and semantic information in Historic Building Information Modeling (HBIM) using the AAT. It develops a method that automatically links elements from a 3D model of a Spanish castle to concepts in the Getty AAT.

Other Getty Vocabularies

ULAN

The AAT is one example, probably the most well-known, of the vocabularies developed by the Getty Institute.

The Union List of Artist Names(ULAN) is a vocabulary that contains records for artists and agents in the cultural landscape, specifically the visual arts. This includes names, relationships, and biographical information for makers and other people and corporate bodies. A record can contain multiple *terms* that may capture [given names, pseudonyms, variant spellings, names in multiple languages, and names that have changed over time](#). A [minimal record](#) contains the following fields: record type, name, name source, display biography, nationality, role, birth date and death date.

See an overview of the ULAN Facets below. Information is taken from the [ULAN documentation](#)

- PERSONS, ARTIST Facet: represents information about individuals involved in the creation or production of works of art or architecture (e.g., *Rembrandt van Rijn*)
- CORPORATE BODIES Facet: represents information about corporate bodies, defined as two or more people working together to create or produce art or architecture (e.g., *Adler and Sullivan*)
- NON-ARTISTS Facet: mostly represents patrons, who often had input in the creative process, and occasionally donors, sitters, and others whose names are required for indexing visual works but who are themselves not artists.
- UNKNOWN PEOPLE BY CULTURE Facet: refers to the generic culture in which a work was created (e.g. *unknown Aztec*, or simply *Aztec*)
- UNIDENTIFIED NAMED PEOPLE Facet: people or corporate bodies where the identity is knowable, but has not yet been thoroughly researched

Records may be linked through associative relationships, including professional relationships (e.g. *assistant of, influenced*) and familial relationships (e.g. *child of, sibling of*). See [here](#) for an example of an ULAN record.

The ULAN is also available as Linked Open Data and can be accessed through the SPARQL Endpoint. Most of the ULAN records are in English but notes and descriptions are sometimes translated to other languages, including Dutch.

AAT and Data Station SSH

In the context of DANS Data Station SSH, the AAT can provide data depositors with a large set (around 74k) of stable concepts, through which they can describe the content and context of their datasets. Although the scope of the AAT is focused on "*concepts* related to ... art, architecture, and other visual cultural heritage, including related disciplines dealing with visual works, such as archaeology and conservation"¹, the breadth of its scope makes it suitable to

¹ <https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/aat/about.html#scope>

SSH domains. For instances, the AAT "[housing \(concept\)](#)" is used to describe the dataset "Woononderzoek Nederland 2024 - woningmarktmodule- release 1.0", <https://doi.org/10.17026/SS/ZBPTLH>. Its integration into the DANS Data Station SSH has also been a long-standing user request.

The use of such AAT concepts a keyword terms, has the potential to:

- Provide a large set of concepts, across domains, to describe datasets
- Give an insight into the content of datasets, without having to inspect their data
- Allow datasets to be grouped under the "Keyword Getty AAT" facet.
- Allow datasets described by Getty AAT concepts to be combined with other, related digital resources, if they have been described by the same concepts.

Audience
[Modern and contemporary history \(2,849\)](#)
[Social sciences \(2,547\)](#)
[Sociology \(1,783\)](#)
[Humanities \(1,489\)](#)
[History \(1,190\)](#)

[More...](#)

Keyword Getty AAT
[oral history \(discipline\) \(4\)](#)
[Contemporary \(style of art\) \(2\)](#)
[housing \(concept\) \(1\)](#)
[applied moldings \(1\)](#)
[dwellings \(1\)](#)

Challenges

The integration of AAT terms onto the Data Station SSH for the purpose of describing datasets, is not straightforward. There are some challenges to its integration, namely:

- **Size:** the AAT contains more than 70.000 records and many records that are not useful as keywords, such as Facet, HierarchyName, and GuideTerm records.
- **Custom hierarchical structure:** The Getty AAT does not use the common SKOS properties `skos:broader` and `skos:narrower` to denote the hierarchical relations between its concepts. Instead, it uses its custom hierarchical properties `gpv:narrower` and `gpv:broader`. Although SPARQL queries, based on SKOS properties are possible, if inference is enabled, their absence makes it challenging to have the AAT concepts to be

served by software such as [SKOSMOS](#), which DANS uses to serve controlled vocabularies to the Data Station SSH.

- **Preserving and presenting the users with AAT under its original hierarchical structure** is challenging, if we want to offer the AAT concepts as keywords, via a simple and user-friendly interface.
- **Nested language labels:** The Getty AAT uses a nested structure for its language labels. In other words, the language labels of a concept are not strings of text, but instance of `skosxl:Label` class, for each language. Those `skosxl:Label` instances are where the labels, as strings of text, are located under the property `xl:literalForm`. Although this structure allows the language label to include information, such as the label authors, it makes it more challenging to retrieve the human readable labels of a concept.
- Each concept includes large amounts of information, such as change notes, dates of edits, contributors, etc, which are not relevant to our use case.

Art and Architecture Thesaurus Concepts (AATC) Controlled Vocabulary

In order to address the issues mentioned above, we had to take some drastic measures and manipulate the original AAT into a derivative semantic artifact, which would suit our use case. Our approach was to create a *slim* of the Getty AAT, a trimmed-down version of the original thesaurus, focused only on concepts, containing a simplified schema for language labels, only in English and Dutch, and relinquish the hierarchy in favor of a flat list of concepts. To avoid confusion, we named this derivative of the AAT semantic artifact Art and Architecture Thesaurus Concepts (AATC).

In concrete terms, the AATC is a SKOS concept scheme that restructures the concepts from the Art and Architecture Thesaurus (AAT) into a flat controlled vocabulary, and excludes non-concepts, such as facets, hierarchies and guide terms. The result is a controlled vocabulary where each term is a `skos:Concept`, member of `aatc:skos:ConceptScheme`, with `English(@en)` and `Dutch(@nl)` labels. And the custom hierarchical relations were replaced by common SKOS properties `skos:broader` and `skos:narrower`.

The AATC URI <https://vocabularies.dans.knaw.nl/aatconcepts/> is created based on URL and convention of DANS Skomos server, but original URIs are kept, so that users are encouraged to find more information and reference the term through its URI.

The resulting AATC can be browsed in DANS [SKOSMOS server](#), viewed as an [RDF turtle file](#), regenerated by using the [aatc_generate.py](#) script, or simply used as keywords in the DANS Data Station SSH.

Alphabetical Hierarchy Groups

atarpieces
 altars (religious fixtures)
 altepemeh
 alter egos
 alteration (process and technique)
 alterations (object components)
 alternate descriptors (controlled vocabulary)
 alternate titles
 alternating gradient synchrotrons
 alternative comics
 alternative dates
 alternative publications
 alternative spaces
 alternative text
 alternative titles
 Alterswert
 althorns
 altimeters
 Altingiaceae (family)
 alto
 alto recorders
 alto saxophones
 altocumulus clouds
 Altoperuvian
 altostratus clouds
 alum
 alumina

Vocabulary information

TITLE	The Art and Architecture Thesaurus Concepts
CREATOR	http://orcid.org/0000-0002-7839-3698 http://ror.org/008pnp284
LICENSE	http://opendatacommons.org/licenses/by/1.0/
CREATED	Thursday, February 6, 2025 00:00:00
TYPE	http://www.w3.org/2004/02/skos/core#ConceptScheme
DESCRIPTION	<p>The Art and Architecture Thesaurus Concepts (AATC) is a SKOS concept scheme that restructures the concepts from the Art and Architecture Thesaurus (AAT) into a flat controlled vocabulary, and excludes non-concepts, such as facets, hierarchies and guide terms. The result is a controlled vocabulary where each term is a skos:Concept, member of aat: skos:ConceptScheme, with English(@en) and Dutch(@nl) labels. Original URI are kept, and users are encourage to find more information and reference the term through its URI. AATC development was motivated by the need to index AAT terms in a Skosmos server, so that AAT terms could be used easily queried via the Skosmos API and easily used by software applications to classify data with AAT terms</p>
URI	http://vocabularies.dans.knaw.nl/aatconcepts

Resource counts by type

Type	Count
Concept	55741
- Deprecated concept	0

Term counts by language

Language	Preferred terms	Alternate terms	Hidden terms
English	55505	0	0
Dutch	42706	0	0

```

aat:300444043 a skos:Concept ;
  skos:inScheme <http://vocabularies.dans.knaw.nl/aatconcepts> ;
  skos:prefLabel "smuggling"@en ;
  dct:issued "2021-05-10T16:23:44"^^xsd:dateTime ;
  skos:prefLabel "smokkelarij"@nl .

aat:300444044 a skos:Concept ;
  skos:inScheme <http://vocabularies.dans.knaw.nl/aatconcepts> ;
  skos:prefLabel "press (culture-related concept)"@en ;
  dct:issued "2021-05-06T15:44:38"^^xsd:dateTime ;
  skos:prefLabel "pers"@nl .

aat:300444045 a skos:Concept ;
  skos:inScheme <http://vocabularies.dans.knaw.nl/aatconcepts> ;
  skos:prefLabel "shipping companies"@en ;
  dct:issued "2021-05-10T17:01:56"^^xsd:dateTime ;
  skos:prefLabel "rederijen"@nl .

aat:300444047 a skos:Concept ;
  skos:inScheme <http://vocabularies.dans.knaw.nl/aatconcepts> ;
  skos:prefLabel "stimulants"@en ;
  dct:issued "2021-05-10T17:02:53"^^xsd:dateTime ;
  skos:prefLabel "genotmiddelen"@nl .

```

Social Sciences and Humanities ^

Keyword Getty AAT ⓘ

Keyword ELSST ⓘ

Topic Classification CESSDA ⓘ

Universe ⓘ

Add a Term

- Animal Style (Greek vase painting style), <http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300265011>
- arrow vases, <http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300265436>
- automobile vases, <http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300420508>
- bilingual (vase painting), <http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300266750>
- black-figure vase painting (image-making), <http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300387209>
- black-figure vase paintings (visual works), <http://vocab.getty.edu/aat/300387206>

AATC Creation & Validation

The Jupyter notebook [aatc_generation.ipynb](#) documents the AATC generation process, via CONSTRUCT SPARQL query, that transforms the query result onto a new structure, saved in the RDF based turtle (.ttl) format. The script [aatc_generate.py](#) only performs the generation of the AATC. The script [aatc_validate.py](#) performs the validation of the AATC against the [aatc_shacl.ttl](#) SHACL rules. If the validation fails, script will output an AssertionError.

